

The Influence of Product Display and Shopping Lifestyle on Impulse Buying at the OH!SOME Store in Malang City

Yumna Tsabitah Ayu Nastiti¹, Achmad Zaini², Ita Rifiani Permatasari³

^{1,2,3}Marketing Management Study Program, Majoring of Business Administration, State Polytechnic of Malang

¹[yumnatasabitah08@gmail.com](mailto:yumnatsabitah08@gmail.com), ²achmad.zaini@polinema.ac.id, ³ita_rifiani@polinema.ac.id

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the influence of product display and shopping lifestyle on impulse buying among customers of OH!SOME Store in Malang City. This research used an explanatory method with a quantitative approach. Data collection was conducted through questionnaires and analyzed using multiple linear regression. The sampling method used was non-probability sampling with a purposive sampling technique, involving 110 respondents.

Corresponding Author:

Yumna Tsabitah Ayu Nastiti

The results showed that both product display and shopping lifestyle had a partial and significant effect on impulse buying. Product display and shopping lifestyle had a simultaneous and significant effect on impulse buying. It can be concluded that customers of OH!SOME Store in Malang City tend to make impulsive purchases when influenced by attractive product displays and an active shopping lifestyle. Therefore, it is essential to continuously improve aesthetic product displays and create an enjoyable shopping experience.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, economic growth has progressed quickly, and the retail and shopping sectors have seen significant development, contributing positively to the economy (Sudjawoto et al., 2024). The retail industry in Indonesia holds great potential, supported by government policies that foster its growth. However, this has led to fierce competition, as the retail business continues to expand each year and is expected to keep growing in the future (Sudarsono, 2017).

One of the retail sectors that has shown significant growth is retail with a lifestyle concept. Lifestyle represents a part of human secondary needs that can change depending on the times or a person's desire to alter their lifestyle. One of the foreign modern retailers entering Indonesia is KKV, which has now rebranded to OH! SOME with bright yellow store colors. OH! SOME is an international lifestyle brand expanding a new concept in retail by combining trendy shopping and photo opportunities, supported by unique and Instagram-worthy interior designs (Katadata.co.id, 2024).

The rebranding from KKV to OH!SOME represents a major shift in brand positioning. While KKV focused on family-oriented dining, OH!SOME embraces a more dynamic and modern concept that blends food with lifestyle. By adopting a fresh and trendy name, OH!SOME aims to attract modern consumers who prefer brands that match their lifestyle. One of the biggest advantages of this rebranding is the ability to target a wider market (Jakartainside.com, 2024).

With this rebranding, OH!SOME aims to enhance its appeal and encourage more spontaneous shopping behaviors. The combination of visually appealing product displays and a trendy shopping environment plays a crucial role in influencing consumer decisions, particularly in triggering impulse buying. Consumers who visit the store with a specific shopping list often find themselves making unplanned purchases due to the attractive store layout, aesthetic appeal, and engaging in-store experience.

Considering this phenomenon, the researcher finds it essential to study how product display as an external factor and shopping lifestyle as an internal factor contribute to impulse buying at OH!SOME Malang. The store's transformation through rebranding has created a retail environment that encourages spontaneous purchases, making it an ideal case study to analyze consumer behavior. This study aims to explore the relationship between product display, shopping lifestyle, and impulse buying, ultimately providing insights into the effectiveness of OH!SOME's rebranding strategy in influencing consumer purchasing decisions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Marketing

According to Juliana et al., (2022), marketing encompasses the entire system aimed at planning and determining prices, as well as promoting and distributing goods and services to meet the needs of both actual and potential buyers. Another opinion by Setiawan et al. (2024:91), marketing is a process involving the analysis, planning, implementation, coordination, and control of marketing programs, including product, pricing, promotion, and distribution strategies.

Consumer Behavior

Kotler and Keller (2016) explain that consumer behavior is the study of how individuals, groups, and organizations select, use, and evaluate goods, services, ideas, or experiences to meet their needs and engage in activities. Another opinion by Basuni et al. (2023), consumer behavior serves as the foundation for consumers in making purchasing decisions. Consumer behavior is closely related to the process of purchasing goods or services.

Product Display

According to Ariyanti et al., (2021), display is one of the steps in arranging merchandise in a store by considering various factors such as the type and benefits of the product, product neatness, and visual appeal, to attract consumers to pick up and purchase the product. The dimensions for measuring product display according to Pentecost & Andrews (2009) as cited in Ningsih (2019) are as follows: 1) Visibility, 2) Accessibility, 3) Neatness of Product Arrangement, 4) Visual appeal.

Shopping Lifestyle

According to Japariato & Sugiharto (2011:33) as cited in Sopiyan & Kusumadewi (2020), shopping lifestyle refers to an individual's attitude or choice in using or spending their money to purchase a product. Economically, shopping lifestyle represents the method chosen by a person to allocate their income, including the distribution of funds for various products and services. According to Diah Pradiatiningtyas (2019), as cited from Suwarman (2003), shopping lifestyle can be measured using the following indicators, as follows: 1) Activities, 2) Interests, 3) Opinions.

Impulse Buying

According to (Mansur et al., 2024) impulse buying is defined as a purchase made without prior conscious recognition, resulting from a decision or intention to buy that was formed before entering the store. Impulse buying occurs when a shopper makes a sudden decision to purchase something, often driven by impulse and happening quickly. According to Lestari (2018), there are four factors that influence impulse buying behavior: 1) Spontaneity, 2) Attraction, Urge, and Intensity, 3) Excitement and Trigger, 4) Disregard for Consequences.

Hypothesis Formulation

H1 : It is suspected that product display has a positive partial effect on impulse buying at the OH!SOME Store in Malang City.

Research conducted by Nur Indah & Achmad Zaini (2023), which found that visual merchandising and product display significantly influence impulse buying at Miniso Mall Olympic Garden Malang. Similarly, Sudjawoto et al. (2024) revealed that attractive product displays have a positive impact on consumers' spontaneous purchase decisions at Indomaret Malang.

H2 : It is suspected that shopping lifestyle has a positive partial effect on impulse buying at the OH!SOME Store in Malang City.

Research conducted by Ningrum & Pudjoprastyono (2023), who discovered that a strong shopping lifestyle positively influences impulse buying among Shopee users. Lailla & Sugeng (2022) and Alimudin et al. (2023) also concluded that consumers with active and hedonic shopping lifestyles are more likely to engage in impulsive buying behavior.

H3 : It is suspected that product display and shopping lifestyle have a simultaneous positive effect on impulse buying at the OH!SOME Store in Malang City.

Research conducted by the combined findings of Nur Indah & Achmad Zaini (2023) and Sudjawoto et al. (2024) for product display, as well as Ningrum & Pudjoprastyono (2023) and Alimudin et al. (2023) for shopping lifestyle. Their studies indicate that both external (store layout and display) and internal (shopping habits and preferences) factors contribute significantly to impulsive consumer behavior.

III. METHOD

This research applies a quantitative method based on the identified problems and objectives. Quantitative research focuses on studying specific populations and samples. Data collection is carried out using research instruments, and the analysis is performed using statistical techniques (Sugiyono, 2017). This study examines the influence of Product Display and Shopping Lifestyle on

Impulse Buying at OH!SOME Store in Malang City. It uses explanatory research, which focuses on explaining the causal relationship between variables (Afifah, 2022).

The population in this study is categorized as an infinite population because the exact amount cannot be determined. The population in this study consists of general customers of the OH!SOME store in Malang City, with a sample of 110 respondents selected through purposive sampling which is the selection of samples based on specific characteristics (Sugiyono, 2017). The criteria for respondents include customers who have visited the OH!SOME store in Malang and have purchased OH!SOME products at least once.

Data were collected using a questionnaire consisting of statements related to product display, shopping lifestyle, and impulse buying, measured using a five-point Likert scale. The research instrument was tested for validity and reliability, followed by descriptive analysis, classical assumption testing, multiple linear regression analysis, coefficient of determination testing, and hypothesis testing.

IV. RESULTS

Validity Test

According to Sugiyono (2017), validity is defined as the degree of alignment between the data collected by the researcher and the actual data observed in the research object. In this study, the total number of samples (n) is 110 respondents, and the degrees of freedom (df) are calculated using the formula $df = n - 2$, resulting in $df = 110 - 2 = 108$. With $df = 108$ and a significance level of 0.05 (5%), the critical r table value is 0.1874. The following are the results of the validity test using IBM SPSS Statistics 26:

Table 1. Validity Test Results

Variable	Item	r count	r table	Sig.	Information
Product Display (X1)	X1.1.1	0.657	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	X1.1.2	0.655	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	X1.2.1	0.559	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	X1.2.2	0.707	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	X1.3.1	0.582	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	X1.3.2	0.585	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	X1.4.1	0.585	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	X1.4.2	0.608	0.1874	0.000	Valid
Shopping Lifestyle (X2)	X2.1.1	0.764	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	X2.1.2	0.838	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	X2.1.3	0.607	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	X2.2.1	0.663	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	X2.2.2	0.551	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	X2.3.1	0.647	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	X2.3.2	0.700	0.1874	0.000	Valid
Impulse Buying (Y)	Y1.1.1	0.559	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	Y1.1.2	0.745	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	Y1.1.3	0.715	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	Y1.2.1	0.794	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	Y1.2.2	0.702	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	Y1.2.3	0.640	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	Y1.3.1	0.620	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	Y1.3.2	0.582	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	Y1.4.1	0.721	0.1874	0.000	Valid
	Y1.4.2	0.591	0.1874	0.000	Valid

Source : Processed Data (2025)

Based on Table 1, the validity test results show that all the questionnaire items used to measure the variables Product Display (X1), Shopping Lifestyle (X2), and Impulse Buying (Y) are valid. This is proven by the fact that all item scores have a correlation value $r\text{-count} > r\text{-table value}$ (0.1874) and a significance level < 0.05 .

Reliability Test

Reliability is a tool to measure a questionnaire which is an indicator of a variable or construct. Respondents' answers to questions are said to be reliable if each question is answered consistently. If the variable being studied has a Cronbach Alpha (α) > 0.6 then the variable is said to be reliable, otherwise if Cronbach Alpha (α) < 0.6 then the variable can be said to be unreliable.

The following are the results of the reliability test using IBM SPSS Statistics 26:

Table 2. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach Alpha	Standart	Information
Product Display (X1)	0.764	0.6	Reliable
Shopping Lifestyle (X2)	0.812	0.6	Reliable
Impulse Buying (Y)	0.863	0.6	Reliable

Source : Processed Data (2025)

Based on Table 2, the results of the reliability test show that all variables have a Cronbach's alpha value > 0.6. This indicates that the items used in this study are reliable. Reliability means that the items used to measure the variables Product Display (X1), Shopping Lifestyle (X2), and Impulse Buying (Y) can be trusted and consistently used as accurate measurement tools in this research.

Normality Test

According to Ghozali (2018:161), the purpose of the Normality Test is to determine whether the residuals or error terms in a regression model are normally distributed. The normality of the data can be assessed visually through graphs, if the data points in a normal probability plot lie close to the diagonal line and follow its direction, or if the histogram shows a bell-shaped curve, then the regression model can be considered to meet the normality assumption. The normality test results in this study are shown in the image below:

Figure 1. Normality Test Result

Figure 2. Histogram of Normality Test

Source : IBM SPSS Statistic 26, Processed Data (2025)

Source : IBM SPSS Statistic 26, Processed Data (2025)

Based on the figure 1 & 2 normality test results, the data points are spread around and follow the direction of the diagonal line in the normality plot, and the histogram shows a normal distribution pattern. This indicates that the linear regression model in this study meets the normality assumption.

Multicollinearity Test

According to Ghozali (2018:107), the purpose of the multicollinearity test is to determine whether there is a correlation between independent variables in a regression model. A good regression model should not show any correlation between its independent variables. The results of the multicollinearity test in this study can be seen in table as follows:

Table 3. Multicollinearity Test Result

Independent Variable	Collinearity Statistics		Information
	Tolerance	VIF	
Product Display (X1)	0.759	1.318	There is no multicollinearity
Shopping Lifestyle (X2)	0.759	1.318	

Source : Processed Data (2025)

Based on the table 3, the results of the multicollinearity test show that the tolerance values for the Product Display and Shopping Lifestyle variables are > 0.10, and the VIF values are < 10. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity among the independent variables.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroskedasticity test aims to determine whether there is an unequal variance of residuals across observations in a regression model (Ghozali, 2018:137). If the residual variance remains constant across observations, it is called homoscedasticity; otherwise, it is referred to as heteroskedasticity. The presence of heteroskedasticity can be identified using a scatterplot of predicted independent variable values against residuals. The following are the results of the heteroscedasticity test in this study using the graphical method:

Figure 3. Heteroscedasticity Test Result

Source : IBM SPSS Statistic 26, Processed Data (2025)

From the figure 3, the heteroscedasticity test results indicate that the points are spread randomly and do not form a specific pattern, with their positions scattered above and below zero on the Y-axis. This suggests that the regression model does not show signs of heteroscedasticity.

Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression is a mathematical model used to describe the relationship between one dependent/response variable (Y) and two or more independent/predictor variables (X1, X2,..., Xn). In this study, the independent variables are Product Display (X1) and Shopping Lifestyle (X2), while the dependent variable is Impulse Buying (Y). The following presents the results of data processing using IBM SPSS Statistics 26:

Table 4. Multiple Regression Analysis Result

Model	B	Std. Error
Constant	12.102	4.546
Product Display (X1)	0.170	0.144
Shopping Lifestyle (X2)	0.766	0.129

Source : Processed Data (2025)

Based on the table 19, the results of multiple linear regression analysis tests can be known linear regression equation as follows:

$$Y = 12.102 + 0.170 X1 + 0.766 X2 + e$$

Y = the dependent variable whose value will be obtained from the independent variable. In this study, the dependent variable is Impulse Buying whose value will be predicted by the independent variables, namely Product Display and Shopping Lifestyle. Based on the equation above, it can be explained that:

1. Constant Value (a) = 12.102

The constant of 12.102 means that if all independent variables, namely Product Display (X1) and Shopping Lifestyle (X2) are ignored or assumed to be 0 (zero), then the Impulse Buying (Y) variable will be equal to its constant value of 12.102.

2. Product Display Variable Regression Coefficient (b1) = 0.170

The multiple regression coefficient value of Product Display (X1) of 0.170 is positive. This means that if there is an increase in value by 1 unit in the Product Display (X1) variable and the Shopping Lifestyle (X2) variable is assumed to be 0 (zero), the Impulse Buying (Y) variable will increase by 0,170.

3. Shopping Lifestyle Variable Regression Coefficient (b2) = 0.766

The Shopping Lifestyle (X2) multiple regression coefficient value of 0.766 is positive. This means that if there is an additional value of 1 unit on the Shopping Lifestyle (X2) variable and the Product Display (X1) variable is assumed to be 0 (zero), the Impulse Buying (Y) variable will increase by 0.766.

Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis, the Product Display (X1) variable and the Shopping Lifestyle (X2) variable that has the greatest contribution or effect on Impulse Buying (Y) is Shopping Lifestyle (X2) with a coefficient of 0.766 compared to Product Display (X1) with a coefficient of 0.170.

Determinant Analysis (coefficient of determination)

The coefficient of determination (r^2) is used to measure how well a regression model explains the variation in the dependent variable or the percentage of the variation in the dependent variable (Y) that can be explained by the independent variable (X) (Rahman et al., 2016). The following presents the results of data processing using IBM SPSS Statistics 26:

Table 5. Coefficient of Determination Result (R^2)

Model	R Square	Adjusted R Square
1	0.348	0.336

Source : Processed Data (2025)

Based on the table 5, the coefficient of determination (R^2) shows that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.336 and the R^2 value is 0.348. This indicates that Product Display and Shopping Lifestyle contribute 33.6% to Impulse Buying at OH!SOME store Malang, while the remaining 66.4% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

Partial Test (T test)

According to Ghozali (2018), the T-test aims to determine the extent to which an independent variable individually affects the dependent variable. For t table determined with $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%), the number of samples of 110 (n) is with df (degree of freedom) = $(\alpha/2; n-k-1 = 0.05/2; 110-2-1 = 0.025; 107 = 1.982)$, n is the number of samples and k is the number of independent variables. With this, the result for t table is 1.982. The following presents the results of data processing using IBM SPSS Statistics 26:

Table 6. Partial Test (T test) Result

Variable	t count	t table	Sig	Sig level	Information
Product Display (X1)	4.096	1.982	0.000	0.05	Significant
Shopping Lifestyle (X2)	7.451	1.982	0.000	0.05	Significant

Source : Processed Data (2025)

Based on the table 21, the t-test results for the Product Display and Shopping Lifestyle variables on Impulse Buying are as follows:

- Hypothesis 1 is accepted. This is proven by the t-value of the Product Display variable (X1), which is greater than the t-table value ($4.096 > 1.982$) and has a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$. Therefore, it can be concluded that Product Display has a partial and significant effect on Impulse Buying at OH!SOME Store Malang.
- Hypothesis 2 is accepted. This is shown by the t-value of the Shopping Lifestyle variable (X2), which is also greater than the t-table value ($7.451 > 1.982$), and a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, it can be concluded that Shopping Lifestyle has a partial and significant effect on Impulse Buying at OH!SOME Store Malang.

Simultaneous Test (F test)

The F-test essentially determines whether all independent variables included in the model collectively have a significant impact on the dependent variable (Rahman et al., 2016). For f table determined with $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%), the number of samples of 110 (n) is with df (degree of freedom) = $(\alpha/2; n-k-1 = 0.05/2; 110-2-1 = 0.025; 107 = 3.08)$, n is the number of samples and k is the number of independent variables. With this, the result for f table is 3.08. The following presents the results of data processing using IBM SPSS Statistics 26:

Table 7. Simultaneous Test (F test) Result

f count	f table	Sig	Significance level	Information
28.566	3.08	0.000	0.05	Significant

Source : Processed Data (2025)

Based on table 7, simultaneous hypothesis testing (F test) above, it can be concluded that: H_a for H_3 is accepted and H_0 is rejected. This is because f count > f table of $28.566 > 3.08$ and significant $0.000 < 0.05$. Therefore, it can be concluded that Product Display and Shopping Lifestyle simultaneously influence impulse buying at OH!SOME store Malang.

V. DISCUSSION

1. The Influence of Product Display on Impulse Buying

The results of this study show that Product Display (X1) has a positive influence on Impulse Buying (Y). This is supported by the multiple regression analysis and the partial t-test, which indicate that better product displays increase the chance of unplanned purchases at OH!SOME Store Malang. This effect is stronger among certain respondent characteristics. Most of the respondents in

this study were female, aged 17–25 years, and students. This finding is supported by the t-test results, where the t-value > t-table value is $7,451 > 1,982$, and the significance value is $0,000 < 0,05$. This confirms that there is a significant effect between the implementation of shopping lifestyle and the increase in impulse buying. This study is supported by the concept of product display as described by Widyana and Nurhidayati (2022), who define it as a technique used to arrange products in an appealing manner to capture buyers' attention and encourage them to make a purchase. The findings of this research are also in line with a previous study by Sudjawoto et al. (2024), which showed that product display has a positive and significant influence on impulse buying. Based on all the data collected, it can be concluded that product display has a positive and significant effect on impulse buying among customers of OH!SOME store Malang.

2. The Influence of Shopping Lifestyle on Impulse Buying

The results of this study show that Shopping Lifestyle (X2) has a positive influence on Impulse Buying (Y). This is supported by the multiple regression analysis and partial t-test, which show that people with a strong shopping lifestyle are more likely to make unplanned purchases at OH!SOME Store Malang. This is especially true for respondents who are female, aged 17–25, and mostly students. This group likes to shop not only for what they need, but also for fun, to express themselves, or to spend time with friends. This finding is supported by the t-test results, where the t-value > t-table value is $7,451 > 1,982$, and the significance value is $0,000 < 0,05$. This confirms that there is a significant effect between the implementation of shopping lifestyle and the increase in impulse buying. This study is supported by the concept of shopping lifestyle as described by Japariato and Sugiharto (2011:33), as cited in Sopiyan and Kusumadewi (2020), which defines shopping lifestyle as an individual's attitude or preference in spending money to purchase products. A consumer's shopping lifestyle reflects their habits, interests, and motivations during shopping activities, all of which can significantly influence impulsive purchasing behavior. The findings of this study are in line with previous research by Ningrum and Pudjoprastyono (2023), which demonstrated that shopping lifestyle has a positive and significant impact on impulse buying. Based on the data collected, it can be concluded that shopping lifestyle plays an important role in driving impulse buying behavior among customers of OH!SOME Store Malang.

3. The Influence of Product Display and Shopping Lifestyle on Impulse Buying

The results of this study show that Product Display (X1) and Shopping Lifestyle (X2) collectively have a positive and significant influence on Impulse Buying (Y). This conclusion is supported by the results of the coefficient of determination analysis and the simultaneous F-test, which demonstrated that these two variables together contribute 33.6% to changes in impulse buying behavior at OH!SOME Store Malang, while the remaining 66.4% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study. Furthermore, based on the simultaneous hypothesis testing, it was found that product display and shopping lifestyle together have a significant positive effect on impulse buying. This is supported by the F-test result, where the f count > f table, which is $28,566 > 3,08$, and the significance value is $0,000 < 0,05$. These findings confirm that both product display and shopping lifestyle simultaneously influence impulse buying behavior at OH!SOME store Malang.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the research conducted through questionnaires, the results indicate that product display and shopping lifestyle significantly influence impulse buying. After completing the validity and reliability tests, along with partial and simultaneous hypothesis testing, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Product display (X1) has a positive partial effect on impulse buying (Y). This means that to increase impulse buying, an effective product display is essential. This includes good visibility, accessibility, neatness of product arrangement, and visual appeal.
2. Shopping lifestyle (X2) has a positive partial effect on Impulse buying (Y). This indicates that promoting a strong shopping lifestyle consisting of shopping activities, customer interest, and opinions can help boost impulse buying behavior.
3. Product display (X1) and Shopping lifestyle (X2) simultaneously have a positive effect on Impulse buying (Y). Therefore, to effectively enhance impulse buying, both an attractive product display and an engaging shopping lifestyle must be well implemented.

VII. SUGGESTIONS

From the research results that have been presented, there are several suggestions that can be used as considerations in conducting further research on the influence of Product display and Shopping lifestyle on Impulse buying. The suggestions are as follows:

1. Based on the results of the research, the lowest average score within the product display variable is found in the item related to harmonious product colors under the neatness of product arrangement indicator. It is recommended that OH!SOME store Malang enhance the visual harmony of product displays by ensuring that color combinations are more aesthetically pleasing and better organized to attract customer attention and improve the overall shopping experience.
2. Based on the research that has been conducted, the lowest average score within the shopping lifestyle variable is found in the frequency of shopping item under the activities indicator. OH!SOME store Malang is expected to increase customer shopping

frequency by implementing strategies such as attractive promotions, loyalty programs, or engaging in-store events that encourage repeat visits and enhance the overall shopping experience.

3. Based on the research that has been conducted, the lowest average score within the impulse buying variable is found in the "overspending" item under the Disregard for Consequences indicator. OH!SOME store Malang is expected to encourage impulse purchases more effectively by offering affordable pricing, clear value propositions, and budget-friendly promotions, allowing customers to feel more comfortable making unplanned purchases without concerns about overspending.

REFERENCES

1. Ariyanti, R., Notoatmojo, M. I., Mulyapradana, A., & S., P. (2021). Pengaruh Potongan Harga Dan Penataan Produk Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Konsumen Di Matahari Departemen Store Pekalongan (Studi Kasus Produk Cardinal Shoes Ladies). *Jurnal Litbang Kota Pekalongan*, 20(1), 55–63.
2. Diah Pradiatiningtyas. (2019). Analisa Pengaruh Hedonic Shopping Value, Shopping Lifestyle, Dan Positive Emotion Terhadap Impulse Buying Konsumen Dalam Melakukan Pembelian Online Di Marketplace. *Journal Speed – Sentra Penelitian Engineering dan Edukasi – Volume 11 No 2 – Mei 2019*
3. Ghozali, I. (2018). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate Dengan Program IBM SPSS 25 (9th ed.)*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
4. Juliana, A. P. (2022). *Dasar-dasar Pemasaran. Pekalongan: PT. Nasya Expanding Management*.
5. Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016). *Marketing Management Global Edition (Vol. 15E)*.
6. Mansur, A. D., Ismail, Y. L., & Abdussamad, Z. K. (2024). Pengaruh Hedonic Shopping Value Dan Shopping Lifestyle Terhadap Impulse Buying Pada Konsumen Butik Zahra Collection. *Jurnal Ilmiah Wahana Pendidikan*, 10(2), 109–120.
7. Ningsih, J. (2019). Pengaruh store atmosphere, display produk dan promosi terhadap pembelian impulsif di mirota kampus yogyakarta. *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Bisnis*, 5(2), 190–203.
8. Pentecost, & Andrews. (2010). Fashion retailing and bottom line: the effects generational cohorts, gender, fashion fanship, attitudes, and impulse buying on fashion expenditure. *Department of Marketing*
9. Purnomo, R. A. (2016). *Analisis Statistik Ekonomi dan Bisnis Dengan SPSS*. Ponorogo: CV. Wade Group.
10. Rahman, A., Yochanan, Samanlangi, A. I., & Purnomo, H. (2016). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif Kualitatif dan R&D*. Alfabeta, Bandung.
11. Sudarsono, J. G. (2017). Pengaruh Visual Merchandising Terhadap Impulse Buying Melalui Positive Emotion Pada Zara Surabaya. *Jurnal Manajemen Pemasaran*, 11(1), 16–25.
12. Sudjawoto, E., Salibbeta, K. K., & Sugiharto, D. P. (2024). Effect of Product Display and Price Discounts on Impulsive Buying. *International Journal of Social Science and Human Research*, 07(01), 144–150.
13. Sugiyono. (2017). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. CV. Alfabeta.
14. Sopiyan, Pipih dan R. Neny Kusumadewi. 2020. Pengaruh Shopping Lifestyle dan Positive Emotion Terhadap Impulse Buying. *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen*, 9(3), 207-216.